

Utilization of digital badge system as a positive reinforcement in new normal teaching among selected grade 9 students

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Abstract

Digital Learning Badges are forms of positive reinforcement which can be used to increase student's engagement and motivation in a virtual class. A badge is typically a graphical icon originally designed by a teacher that appears as a reward for the learner after getting an achievement through class performance as well as to boost confidence and inspires them to show their capabilities without upsetting from teachers' feedbacks. In this study, the researcher selected Grade 9 students from Mariano Marcos Memorial High School, as subjects in the implementation of digital learning badges as a tool to improve academic performance. The use of digital badges in the online learning environment – new normal setup where students were able to solve interactively, automatically assessed exercises in Science class from first to third quarters. The researcher conducted an experiment where the students (N=251) were monitored and normally with and without achievement badges. The total earned badges were counted and assessed if the collected badges affected the final grade. The researcher also collected numerical and open-ended feedbacks to find out students' attitudes towards the received badges. Based on our findings, utilizing digital badges in a e-learning environment served as an effective tool to encourage learners in class discussions and explore their capabilities through messages of encouragements. The research helped to validate students' emotional and mental perspectives by encouraging them to collaborate with others, as well as show and improve their capabilities without the consciousness and anxiety of committing mistakes. Ultimately, this tool helped intrinsically motivate online learners and establish a friendly and conducive e-learning environment.

Keywords: Digital badge system; Positive reinforcement; E-learning motivation; Learning engagement; Online platforms; Synchronous classes; Sticker badges.

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Introduction

According to Sun & Chen (2016), learning can become transformative when educators and students integrate information across disciplines and practices, critically weigh significantly different perspectives, and incorporate various inquiries. Educators can formalize and create such opportunities through fostering critical learning spaces, in which students are encouraged to increase their capacities of analysis, imagination, critical thinking, creative expression, self-awareness, and esteem. Modern approaches and strategies in learning was specifically introduced through online education where activities are designed to be fun, simple, and interactive. Previously, the provisions of inspiring and encouraging messages and stimuli to students are essential in a traditional classroom setting as well as in an online education (Lee & Hammer, 2011). This reinforcement direct behavior towards learning targets, increased effort, energy, initiation, and persistency in lesson activities which affects cognitive process and may enhance academic performance.

In this development, the study will show how the use of badge system in e-learning environments affect desirable learning behaviors. Positive and negative reinforcement method combines with the badge system which delivers corresponding messages to students based on their performance (Hakulinen et al., 2015; Benner, 2017). Digital badges may provide new strand for online educational activities and experiences for students (Gibson et al., 2015). When used with points and leaderboards, a badge can become a gamification facet allowing learners to compete with themselves or others, and to know how close they are to achieving a goal and obtaining its additional status. In this role, digital badges motivate continued engagement, which increases momentum on task and supports skill attainment through their improving performance (Stefaniak & Carey, 2019). Additionally, students can summarize their own achievements in this role of intrinsic character. With these motivational features, digital badges have the potential to become an alternative credentialing system which provides visible recognition in digital symbols that link directly on a digital classroom as evidence of educational achievements protecting a public display for their considering privacy (Pappas, 2017). This research paper defines what digital badges are, its examples and uses, and a total feature on educational affordances.

The objective of this study is to utilize a digital badge system teaching strategy in improving students' academic performance in an e-learning environment of selected Grade 9 students of Mariano Marcos Memorial High School. This is to maintain or promote the learner's interests in learning activities, reinforce them through a ramified solution such as inspiring messages, and maximize the outcomes of the learning process with the 21st century entities. Amidst the COVID-19 Global Outbreak, online education has become essential for continuity of classes. Thus, motivating instructions and credentials should deliver accordingly by creating badge system.

Innovation, Instruction, and Strategy

As Covid-19 shifted the education set-up worldwide, challenges were identified based on what platforms should be used, how teaching should be facilitated and what kind of strategies would fit an e-learning environment. Improving students' performance inside a face-to-face classroom is not a new conflict. Basically, that is a main issue that a teacher should address from time to time. There are different strategies and approaches were introduced to fully solve this problem. As part of giving rewards, teachers usually give sticker badges which is common in the early grades, plus points, not to mention food rewards in some instances for middle students, but the big challenge is grounded on how to sustain their interest in the online learning setup (Seliskar, 2014). This research sought to assess the effectiveness of utilizing a digital badge system as an alternative reinforcement to motivate students in a virtual learning environment.

Research Questions

1. What skills and behaviors do the digital badges represent?
2. What are the effects of a combined reinforcement (positive and negative) with giving badges to response on students' performance?
3. How does the badge system improve students' learning performance in an e-learning environment?

Scope and Limitation

The study was conducted for the purpose of determining the effectiveness of utilizing digital badges as positive reinforcement in improving their learning performance in an e-learning classroom setup. Preferring an alternative rewarding strategy, this should be way to keep the motivating connection and approaches to students even education has shifted in a virtual classroom. This research aimed to assess the students' participation drive inside an online classroom using a digital badge system which is commonly found in interactive game learning sites but not in a basic digital classroom.

Due to time constraints, the whole research process took place within six months the research covered implementation from first to third quarter of school year 2020-2021 but the researcher decided to continue with the implementation of the badges up to the fourth quarter. The studies were conducted among selected Grade 9 Students (Benevolence, Celerio, Diligence, Excellence, and Nationalism Sections) who are officially enrolled in a blended learning modality. This research was to improve participation which is directly proportional to their performance progress and achievements within a science class. Digital badges used were carefully designed and created by the researcher using Canva App and no copyright infringement was done in the use of icons, elements, and objects applied in the badges since they were available on the platform at no extra cost.

The study is limited on the actual data from the earned badges and experience feedback of the students during the pre-survey activity and counting the total earned badges per quarter and in three quarters. This project did not cover different learning sites but utilize the system during synchronous classes preferably and extended to asynchronous classes. Posted certificates for total earned badges are posted in a classwork section of their Google Classroom for data privacy considerations.

The study aims to find out the effectiveness of using the digital badge system and promotes positive reinforcement in a virtual classroom but not ideally solve the problem regarding demotivated students since not all students had an access with Google class since they chose a modular learning modality.

Research Methodology

Participants

Table 1

Number of respondents / participants per section

Section	Number of Participants	Percentage
Celerio	37/37	100%
Benevolence	54/54	100%
Diligence	55/55	100%
Excellence	52/52	100%
Nationalism	55/55	100%
Total	251/251	

The participants of the study were selected Grade 9 students of Mariano Marcos Memorial High School of the Academic Year 2020-2021 currently handled by the researcher. There were a total of 251 student participants based on enrolment with 100% class participation via blended learning set-up which was shown in Table 1.

Data Collection

This study was conducted in two phases via Google Forms and through virtual classes. The first phase focused on asking students to answer a pre-survey question via Google form including the following questions. In this study, both primary and secondary data were used. The primary data were based on students' pre-feedback on positive reinforcement and the secondary data were collected based on students' achievement improvement rate in an online class using badges. Also, student-respondents' perception on the use of badge system in selected Grade 9 students at Mariano Marcos Memorial High School were determined through short responses.

For the collection of data, the following instruments and platforms were used. To sum up, the following step-by-step process were done to fully view the effectiveness of the study.

The teacher conducted a survey or short responses via Google form rating the utilization of digital badge system in an e-learning environment using a Likert Scale and how do their respective teachers motivate them and if they are familiar in badge system or giving badges as rewards inside the classroom. They answered it through google forms.

The teacher gave digital badges based on students' performance (learning and tap badge) after the synchronous or as per checked activities in asynchronous classes. It will be sent out or distributed via their Google Workspace accounts. Google Classroom will be the main virtual environment. It helps implement standards-based learning and differentiated instruction in the classroom. Teacher will attach assignment, examinations or quizzes there and automatically give grade feedback sent through email.

Also, positive reinforcement though messages can be associated as evaluation to students. Low performing students and least mastered competencies were also identified for the teachers' record and focus for improvement. An average grade on all performance was computed and show learners' progress through graph presentation. A short response survey in Google Forms were done to check students' views on how the badge system helped them improve their learning performance - descriptive and quantitative based on the quarterly grades from Quarters 1 to 3.

Figure 1 Research paradigm on the procedures of the study

NOTE: This figure demonstrates the phases and stages of the research conduct from pre-survey to identifying the correlation of earned badges to class performance based on learners' accumulated grades.

Ethical Considerations

According to Willis et al. (2015) from the title *Digital Badges and Ethics: The Uses of Individual Learning Data in Social Contexts*, with the expansion of educational technology, some work is being done at the intersection of ethical theory and learning analytics. Some propose ethical frameworks for development. However, others appeal specifically to known problems in the legal use of student data in analytics systems. This is a growing domain of research in the broader implications of how educational technology affects student growth and development (Dickey, 2005). Though some commentators have noted the potentially harmful aspects of having open data in social networks, to date there has been scant studies of ethical issues in open digital badges. As research in the ethics of educational technology expands, a myriad of potential problems looms.

To bridge this gap, targeted ethical questions must be specific enough to demonstrate applicability, but also be generalizable enough to warrant attention outside of the broadly considered technology. Due to their connection with social networks, availability of meta-data, and transparency of learning, digital badges face important ethical questions best formulated within the larger context of learning analytics (Imran, 2019). This project both focused on students' performance and considered emotions on through tap badges with encouraging words.

In this study, the teacher did not post the badges that are collected publicly but allowed students to collect their badges. The teacher posted the students who belong to the top earned individuals through a certificate and show via Google Classroom.

Presentation and Discussion of Findings / Results

To determine how digital badge system will be utilized in an e-learning environment and its effect on students' learning performance the researcher obtained and identify the effects based on the student's perception via Likert Scale and its relationship to the students in terms of (a) learning drive / reinforcement, (b) encouragement (c) personal experiences, and (d) supporting factors. To determine the effectiveness of the badge system, the researchers determined the number of students who improved in each quarter as well as the mean scores of the mean population grades in three quarter where the results were compared.

Table 2

Summary on pre-survey on students' perception about digital learning badges

Questions	Responses in All Sections
Do you know about digital learning badges?	100% No
Did you receive any digital learning badges (digital or printed) in your previous school years?	100% No
If yes, can you tell how you received it? and describe the digital badge that you have received?	N/A
If no, do you wish to receive some learning badges?	100% Yes
Where can we find badges and who do you think can give it to a student?	At least 95 % of the respondent answered they knew boy scout/girl scout badges, they have only experience receiving only stickers and plus points given by the teacher during classes. 5% answered that they knew digital online game badges but not learning badges.

Table 2 shows the summary of students' responses based on pre-survey questions on their perception about digital badges. This means that 100% of the students were not familiar about digital badges and mostly, they are familiar only with sticker and group or organization badges.

Table 3
Summary results of earned digital badges mean vs. quarter class score grades per quarter

Quarters	Earned Digital Badges (Mean)	Class Score Grades (Mean)
Q1	15	83.33
Q2	22	85.6
Q3	26	87.8
Mean of Three Quarters		85.57

Table 3 shows the mean of grades per quarter and the mean of class grades from first to third quarter. According to the table, Quarter 3 got the highest earned digital badges with 26 and also with the highest class score grade at 87.8, while the overall weighted mean is 85.57 based from 35 distributed digital badges in three quarters.

Table 4
Summary results on descriptive statistics of rating the badge system using Likert scale

Questions	Weighted Mean Value	Verbal Interpretation
1. Receiving learning badges from a teacher is a good motivation for the students.	4.8	Strongly Agree
2. Receiving badges from my teacher satisfies my learning performance and desire to learn more.	5	Strongly Agree
3. Receiving badges encourage me to recite during our synchronous classes.	4	Agree
4. Receiving digital badges can help you to set plans before attending your Science synchronous class.	4	Agree
5. Receiving digital badges recognize my learning efforts and performance inside our virtual classroom.	5	Strongly Agree
6. Receiving digital badges boost my confidence and help me out to speak and participate in the class.	4	Agree
7. Earning more badges can show how I improve my learning performance.	4	Agree
8. I feel happy when I receive badges for the week.	5	Strongly Agree
9. It was challenging when I failed to get my learning badge for the week.	4.1	Agree
10. I am excited to receive more badges.	5	Strongly Agree
11. I want to receive more badges in the future.	4.4	Strongly Agree

Weighted Mean Value Range:

- 4.20-5.00 - Strongly Agree
- 3.40-4.19 - Agree
- 2.60-3.39 - Neither
- 1.80-2.59 - Disagree
- 1- 1.79 - Strongly Disagree

Table 4 shows the summary results on descriptive statistics of rating the badge system using Likert scale. As seen on the table, items 2 (*Receiving badges from my teacher satisfies my learning performance and desire to learn more*), 5 (*Receiving digital badges recognize my learning efforts and performance inside our virtual classroom*), 8 (*I feel happy when I receive badges for the week*), and 10 (*I am excited to receive more badges*) have the highest ratings of 5 with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree". This also shows that majority of the students are positive in receiving their digital learning badges.

Table 5
Summary on students' learning progress

Grade and Section	No. of Students	1st Quarter			2nd Quarter			3rd Quarter		
		Passed	Failed	%	Passed	Failed	%	Passed	Failed	%
9-Celerio	37	37	0	100	37	0	100	37	0	100
9-Benevolence	54	48	6	88.9	51	3	94.4	54	0	100
9-Diligence	55	48	7	87.2	50	5	90.9	54	1	98.18
9-Excellence	52	45	7	92.3	47	5	92.3	51	1	98.07
9-Nationalism	55	37	18	67.2	46	9	83.6	55	0	100

Percentage of Passing: 99.25%

Table 5 shows the learning progress of students from Quarter 1 to Quarter 3 based on total percentage of Passing Rate which is 99.25%. Based on the table above, all of the students from 9-Celerio have passed their grades from first to third quarters. Students from 9-Benevolence and 9-Nationalism have also passed their grades on the third quarter, although the latter section does have some students who failed in the Science class during the first and second quarters.

Figure 2 Total percentage of passing rate in Grade 9 Science, Q1-Q3, SY 2020-2021

The graph above shows the passing rate percentage of students in each quarter. Thus, there is an evident learning progress based on the increase difference of passing rate which is 14.3% (85.12% to 99.25%) from Quarters 1 to 3.

Table 6 shows a strong positive correlation between earned badges and class grade. As the collected earned badges increase, student's class grade improves.

Table 6

Results of Pearson correlation on earned badges, class grades and weighted mean of descriptive statistics

Correlation	Earned Badges	Class Grade Mean
Earned Badges	1.00	0.6938
Class Grade Mean	0.6938	1.00

N=3

*Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Conclusions

This research aimed to utilize a badge system teaching strategy in improving students' academic performance in an e-learning environment. This promote the learner's interests in learning activities and reinforce them through a ramified solution such as inspiring messages and maximize the outcomes of the learning process with the 21st century entities. In this development, the study showed how the use of badge system in e-learning environments affects desirable learning behaviors. Positive and negative reinforcement methods were combined with the badge system which delivered corresponding messages to students based on their performance. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that:

- Teachers can design their own original badges via Canva App, photo collage, PowerPoint or even Adobe application for those who have high skills in photo editing and design.
- It can be a form of image or gif to make it more look catchy and lively. There are some applications which are free for public use and modifications can be done adequately.
- Digital badges were given right after synchronous lessons. Students who answered correctly and participate during the discussion will receive a badge through their Suite accounts. Those students who finished a single lesson especially if under modular modality will also receive badge. Every time the teacher seen a development on a child even in times they lose their confidence, badges will also be sent out to them.
- Digital badges were sent reinforce and encourage students, improve behavior and skills, such as critical thinking and problem-solving, collaboration across networks and leading by influence, agility and adaptability, initiative, effective oral and written communication, accessing and analyzing information, curiosity and imagination. No matter how big or small they have shown, or any mistakes- they will still get the badges.
- This digital badge system uplifts students' confidence, urges them to do what is right inside the classroom and emphasizes that committing mistakes should be seen not as problems but as positive challenges. Distribution of digital badges in an e-learning environment is an effective way to motivate students in participating in virtual classes and an alternative way show learning appraisal. When the teacher encourages students, it adds more confidence to them and reading those words of encouragement present in their collected badges made them feel appreciated and acknowledge. They are challenged to receive the badges in any way they could possibly do.

- Statistically, significant differences were observed in total earned digital badges of the students, the average total number of badges from the average 3 quarter grades. Furthermore, the majority of the students testified being motivated by the digital learning badges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher found out that utilization of digital badge system as positive reinforcement in teaching among selected Grade 9 students of Mariano Marcos Memorial High School was effective with an increase of 11.9% (from 85.12 to 97.02% passing rate) from Quarters 1 to 3. The study further establishes that using the digital badge system can be used as a positive learning reinforcement to improve class performance. With this, the researcher recommended that this study be used:

- as a basis of teachers to encourage learner in class discussions and explore their capabilities through message of encouragements and proof digitally which really fit in virtual classes;
- as a tool to measure the learning progress of the students through total earned badges;
- as a tool to validate their emotional and mental perspectives by encouraging them to do collaboration with others, show and improve their capabilities as expected without thinking of committing mistakes. Thus, intrinsically motivate online learners;
- as guiding principles in establishing a friendly yet conducive e-learning environment;
- as great way to promote positive learning culture and cultivates self-guided learning; and
- as additional visual element to e-learning incentives.

To help the increase of effectiveness points in this study, the researcher also recommends the following:

- Teachers should consider organization culture, that is, focus on students' experiences on receiving badges and communication process to fully adopt this innovative system in a virtual classroom.
- Digital Badge System may be used either per lesson week or for an entire module once students finished it similar as a course requirement.
- Teachers should also give students choices on which they want or like to have after completing the lesson activities or synchronous class discussion which can promote autonomy and motivate the learners to learn.
- Teachers should also award badges to parents and students. This may help the communication process completely with regular follow ups enable staying the process in touch so that no student will fail whichever learning modalities they belong.
- Lastly, this study should be done in a complete school year, Q1 to Q4 to completely achieved the 100% target goals of utilizing the badge system as positive reinforcement in a virtual classroom.

References

- Benner, D. (2017, September 26). *The why's and how's of student badges*. TechNotes. <https://blog.tcea.org/student-learning-badges/>
- Dickey, M. D. (2005). Engaging by design: How engagement strategies in popular computer and video games can inform instructional design. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 53(2), 67-83. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02504866>
- Gibson, D., Ostashewski, N., Flintoff, K., Grant, S., & Knight, E. (2015). Digital badges in education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 20(2), 403-410. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-013-9291-7>
- Hakulinen, L., Auvinen, T., & Korhonen, A. (2015). The effect of achievement badges on students' behavior: An empirical study in a university-level computer science course. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (ijET)*, 10(1), 18-29. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v10i1.4221>
- Imran, H. (2019). Evaluation of awarding badges on student's engagement in gamified e-learning systems. *Smart Learning Environments*, 6(1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-019-0093-2>
- Lee, J. J., & Hammer, J. (2011). Gamification in education: What, how, why bother? *Academic Exchange Quarterly*, 15(2), 146.
- Pappas, C. (2017, June 1). *8 notable benefits of using a badge-based eLearning reward system*. eLearning Industry. <https://elearningindustry.com/notable-benefits-using-badge-based-elearning-reward-system>
- Seliskar, H. V. (2014, May 16). *Using badges in the classroom to motivate learning*. Faculty Focus. <https://www.facultyfocus.com/articles/teaching-with-technology-articles/using-badges-classroom-motivate-learning/>
- Stefaniak, J., & Carey, K. (2019). Instilling purpose and value in the implementation of digital badges in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 44. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0175-9>
- Sun, A., & Chen, X. (2016). Online education and its effective practice: A research review. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 15, 157-190. <https://doi.org/10.28945/3502>
- Willis, J. E., Quick, J. D., & Hickey, D. T. (2015). Digital badges and ethics: The uses of individual learning data in social contexts. In D. Hickey, J. Jovanovic, S. Lonn, and J. E. Willis (Eds.) *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Open Badges in Education* (pp. 41-45). <https://hdl.handle.net/2022/22923>